

DIGITAL LEGAL RELATIONS IN THE IMPLEMENTATION OF CONSULAR PROTECTION

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Abstract. Digital development forms a system of new methods and tools for the implementation of consular protection using the Internet and information and communication technologies, and demonstrates their impact on modern consular practice. The purpose of digitalization in consular practice is to establish and support online contacts with our citizens in foreign countries, to establish an effective system of working with them. In this research, the author concludes that ensuring the security of the mechanisms used in diplomatic and consular activities in the cyberspace is of paramount importance.

Key words: consul, consular protection, consular diplomacy, data protection, cyber law, cyberspace, consular convention, consular service, digital management, digital diplomacy.

Аннотация. Рақамли тараққиёт интернет ва ахборот-коммуникация технологияларидан фойдаланган ҳолда консуллик ҳимоясини амалга оширишнинг янги усуллари ва воситалари тизимини шакллантиради ҳамда уларнинг замонавий консуллик амалиётига таъсирини намён қилади. Консуллик амалиётида рақамлаштириш масаласининг мақсади – хорижий давлатларда бўлиб турган фуқаролар билан онлайн алоқа ўрнатиш ва уларни қўллаб-қувватлаш, фуқаролар билан самарали ишлаш тизимини ташкил этишдир. Мақолада ушбу масалалар таҳлил қилинган ҳамда кибермайдонда дипломатик ва консуллик фаолиятида фойдаланиладиган механизмларнинг хавфсизлигини таъминлаш долзарб аҳамият касб этиши тўғрисида хулоса чиқарилган.

Калит сўзлар: консул, консуллик ҳимояси, консуллик дипломатияси, маълумотларни ҳимоя қилиш, кибер ҳуқуқ, кибер майдон, консуллик конвенцияси, консуллик рўйхати, консуллик хизмати, рақамли дипломатия.

Аннотация. Цифровое развитие формирует систему новых методов и инструментов осуществления консульской защиты с использованием сети Интернет и информационно-коммуникационных технологий и демонстрирует их влияние на современную консульскую практику. Цель цифровизации в консульской практике – установление и поддержка онлайн-контактов с гражданами в зарубежных странах, налаживание эффективной системы работы с ними. Автор делает вывод, что обеспечение безопасности механизмов, используемых в дипломатической и консульской деятельности в киберпространстве, имеет первостепенное значение.

Ключевые слова: консул, консульская защита, консульская дипломатия, защита данных, киберправо, киберпространство, консульская конвенция, консульский учет, консульская служба, цифровая дипломатия.

Consular activity has undergone great and drastic changes in recent years, with unconventional demands. The pandemic and the development of the digital world and its painful points pose complex issues to consuls. In particular, the consul's communication with citizens in foreign countries, their legal literacy, the exchange of information and many other situations that require modern technology, are seen as important tools in the implementation of consular protection. The importance of consular law in international legal relations, like other legal institutions, stems from the nature of the social relations it regulates. The correct application of the norms of the various branches applied in the implementation of consular protection creates a solid legal basis for the sustainable development of relations between states.

The Institute of Consular Protection is an inter-sectoral institute of international law by its legal nature. In the theory of law, an inter-sectoral institution is a set of legal norms aimed at regulating legal relations in several sectors. Intersectoral legal institutions are also known in science as complex, or polyvalent legal networks.

In our opinion, consular protection of civil rights in foreign countries is literally legal protection¹. Such protection is provided by complex, multifaceted and inter-sectoral law enforcement². The protection of a citizen even outside the state is not a simple manifestation of legal protection and legal protection. Such protection is a complex legal protection of a specific nature, which is carried out by the state and goes beyond the borders of the state³.

The protection of the rights of both legal entities and individuals of the Republic of Uzbekistan in foreign countries is an important part of the consular system. In this context, we have found it expedient to study the role of consular protection among emerging branches of international law. In addition, we studied the aspects of consular protection in modern international law, which are developing rapidly and are undergoing drastic changes as a result of the pandemic.

In today's world of regular and active cross-border cooperation, the task of protecting personal

data is not only a national issue, but also a rapidly evolving system of international norms that unites existing concepts and standards.

In-depth analysis of complex global processes and the results of our country's development in the coming years will consist of seven priorities in order to further improve the welfare of our people on the basis of the principle "For Human Dignity", to ensure human rights and interests, to establish active civil society. The Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2026 has been adopted⁴. The document uses a number of concepts, such as "e-government", "digital passport of citizens", "digital public service", "digital office", "digital control", which are of great importance in lawmaking and law enforcement.

New technological realities (digital economy, big data, web networks, cryptocurrencies, cybercrime, virtual objects, digital jurisprudence) have created new challenges and challenges for the legal and regulatory system.

In our view, digital legal relations should create a model of legal regulation that is consistent with this new technological reality. At the same time, special attention should be paid to its adaptation. It is a necessary process for the rapid and formal assimilation of traditional law, law and authority into the new digital conditions of society. This includes the specifics of the rules governing communication on the Internet (customs, technical standards, etc.), compliance, the mechanism of legal regulation, the concept of legal relations and legal liability; digital achievements; the legal nature of a smart contract (smart-contract); looking at artificial intelligence as an object or subject of law; cryptocurrencies (object of rights and measures to protect virtual values); legal liability measures in digital law enforcement; the dangers and threats of the dark network, as well as the need to develop and improve mechanisms to obtain reliable evidence.

A new approach to digital cooperation is also in the focus of the United Nations. In particular, it is stated in the UN Secretary-General's Roadmap⁵ for Digital Cooperation, which is based on high-level

¹ Гафурова С.А. Консуллик ҳимояси институти: монография. – Т.: ЖИДУ, 2020. – 57-бет.

² Кулапов В.Л. Основы теории государства и права. – М., 2002. – С.62.

³ See: Волкова М. С. Дипломатическая защита как элемент международного стандарта в вопросах правового регулирования положения иностранцев // Электронное приложение к "Российскому юридическому журналу" №2/2012 / <http://electronic.ruzh.org>

⁴ See: Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг "2022 – 2026 йилларга мўлжалланган Янги Ўзбекистоннинг тараққиёт стратегияси тўғрисида"ги фармони // 28.01.2022 / lex.uz/ru/docs/5841063.

⁵ United Nations Secretary-General's Roadmap for Digital Cooperation / <https://www.un.org/en/content/digital-cooperation-roadmap>.

panel work on digital cooperation and extensive consultations. The Road Map, in turn, responds to complex and rapid changes; takes into account the development of digital technologies and their impact on the economy and society; highlights ethical issues, including human rights issues, that increase the need for digital collaboration; the emergence of new and advanced technologies intensified the discussion of their contribution to the future; defines the role of the UN in digital relations; sets priorities for human rights, trust and security, and emerging technologies⁶.

Let us also consider the interpretation of the concept of digital diplomacy. Digital (electronic diplomacy (“digital diplomacy” or e-diplomacy)⁷ – means the implementation of diplomatic missions through the use of the Internet and information and communication technologies. Digital diplomacy uses new media, social networks and blogs in the global system. E-diplomacy involves government agencies – primarily foreign policy agencies and non-governmental organizations dealing with foreign relations. The goal of digital diplomacy is to promote foreign policy interests and information and propaganda to the public and the political elite through Internet television, social networks and mobile phones. According to researcher Novikov N.V. “digital diplomacy is aimed at implementing the information tasks of foreign policy in a new context of reality through various communicative practices”⁸. At the same time, it has its downsides, and researchers are discussing the possibility of introducing information boundaries to protect against the negative effects of digital diplomacy.

However, given all the objective advantages of digital technology, the development of cyber relationships in practice is close to risks and threats. The Internet is seen as a channel for spreading

extremism and terrorism, propagating foreign ideology and foreign policy, and waging an information war. The Internet is used as a motivating force when most citizens go abroad.

The tendency to fragment the global information sphere, separating national and regional segments from it, also confirms that cyber relations are perceived as a threat in the international arena.

While cyber technology was thriving even before the pandemic, the world was already in the process of “digital transformation” – the pandemic crisis has significantly accelerated this process and stressed its importance in terms of security. In the near future, digital technologies will continue to grow steadily.

As a continuation of this view, we believe that in cyber relationships, a person becomes impersonal; digital technologies, which, at first glance, make it easier to obtain legal aid, put people and their information at risk of disclosure; the information on the disclosed person is followed by the ground for the crimes of extortion and abuse. At the same time, technology, which was initially only a tool for development, is beginning to play a decisive role in this process.

The development of digital relations, the rapid introduction of high technology into the daily consular practice requires consuls to be aware and should be seen in consular activities as a new technological social dialogue, the breadth and speed of communication with citizens⁹.

From the very beginning of the rapid development of information technology, the concept of open government has spread around the world – the emphasis has been placed on the ideals of transparency and accountability in governance. At the same time, citizens had to use government documents and procedures to create an effective inspection system¹⁰.

⁶ https://unctad.org/system/files/official-document/a76d64_ru.pdf

⁷ See more: Барышников Д.Н., Туленков А.Ю. “Цифровая дипломатия” и государственный суверенитет в эпоху глобализации // Вестник Санкт-Петербургского университета. Серия 6. Политология. Международные отношения. Выпуск 4. 2012.; Сурма И.В. Цифровая дипломатия в мировой политике // Государственное управление. Электронный вестник. Выпуск № 49. 2015.; Alex Oliver. “Travelling responsibly, but further to go: Australia’s new consular diplomacy”. // Issue 6 of the Australian Journal of International Affairs titled Australia’s New Consular Diplomacy. Volume 70. 2017.

⁸ Новиков Н.В. Коммуникативные стратегии цифровой дипломатии. Автореферат дисс. на сосис. уч.степ. к.и.н. – М., 2017.

⁹ Ровинская Т. Роль новых цифровых технологий в период кризиса // Мировая экономика и международные отношения, 2021, т. 65, № 6.

¹⁰ See more: Report Global Consular Forum 2015 Tuesday 26 – Thursday 28 May 2015 | WP1381 Held at the Hacienda Fiesta Americana San Antonio El Puente, Cuernavaca, Mexico <https://www.wiltonpark.org.uk/wp-content/uploads/WP1381-Report.pdf>; Seoul Consensus Statement on Consular Cooperation October 27, 2016. <http://globalconsularforum.com/wp-content/uploads/2016/03/Seoul-Consensus-Statement-on-Consular-Cooperation.pdf>.

Over the last two decades, this concept has become inextricably linked to the concept of “e-government”, with the common goals of “open” and “e-government” being to increase efficiency and transparency in providing legal assistance to the population, as well as simplification and improvement of legislation.

Following the current practice of consular offices of the Republic of Uzbekistan abroad, the following can be seen about the difficulties in the implementation of information technology.

In the course of our research, we have recognized that the development of diplomacy can benefit from high-tech change. The Internet is becoming an indispensable tool for diplomatic negotiations and communication with various stakeholders. In this new context, the traditional law of diplomacy and consular affairs must also be developed through a new interpretation of existing rules. If some of these rules are insufficient or insufficient to regulate cyber relationships, new rules need to be created. International rules on the inviolability of buildings, the inviolability of documents and archives, freedom of official correspondence, tax exemptions and inviolability of the judiciary must be reinterpreted and applied to reflect the cyber diplomacy environment. In addition, new rules of immunity

should be created for the “cyber diplomatic or consular suitcase”.

Digital development forms a system of new methods and tools for the implementation of consular protection using the Internet and information and communication technologies, and demonstrates their impact on modern consular practice. The purpose of digitalization in consular practice is to establish and support online contacts with citizens in foreign countries, to establish an effective system of working with them. It is also used in diplomatic and consular activities in cyberspace.

In conclusion, if a positive solution is not achieved as a result of direct step-by-step protection within the institute of consular protection, the problem will be resolved through diplomatic means and peaceful means of resolving disputes in international law. However, this does not mean that the duties of the consul will be suspended. The consul will not lose his activism on this issue, but will ensure that the state uses other means of protection under international law.

It is worth noting that as a result of the above research and our conclusions, given the expansion of cyberspace and the development of information exchange, it is necessary to form a constructive dialogue between the consul and citizens.

